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Quality Assessment of Preschool Education in the Republic of Tatarstan

S.N. Bashinova * (a), E.A. Sadretdinova (b)

(a) Kazan Federal University, Kazan, Russia

(b) Nursery School No. 113, Kazan, Russia

Abstract

The year of 2018 is special for the Russian Federation since the country entered the Decade of Childhood. Preschool education that is a nursery school is the environment in which children are submerged and where they feel comfortable; this is the first public-state form to provide for professional and educational work with the younger generation. After all, the prosperous future of each state, civilization and the whole world depends on the growing generation, its harmonious development. Research shows that the full development of the child depends on the two components of his/her life - a two-parent family and a nursery school. Considering the gradually improving demographic situation in Russia, the demand for educational services at the nursery school is constantly growing.

Keywords: quality assessment, preschool education.

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Introduction

Today quality assessment of preschool education occupies a leading position in the discussion of issues of pre-school education. One of the most important facts in the international debate was a well-known study of the impact of the High / Scope program on the life performance of its advocates J. Heckman, F. Cunha, L. Lochner, D. Masterov, which in fact approved the critical significance of educating small children from the point of view of the of their whole future life.

It became clear for the society that education is very important. The well-known expression “having saved on schools, we will go broke on prisons” has received “apagogical argument”. At the same time, the earlier investments are made, the greater the rate of profit, expressed in the further

* Corresponding author. Tel.: E-mail address: svetlana-bashinova@mail.ru

development of human capital, can be expected. Researchers have proved that it is easy to be late with such investments in human capital: the last chance to return the invested capital and get a small profit from the investment in the education of first-grade children. The later capital is invested in a child, the less profitable all investments become. The results of these studies served as a basis for politicians in many countries to make very important decisions about the transformation of preschool services into the system of preschool education. Thus, a “preschool boom” has arisen in the world.

There were questions: How much will the results depend on how hard you worked with the children? How to educate children? What is to be done to achieve improvement in their performance over a lifetime? What preschool programs could achieve the desired results? That is how the problem of the quality of preschool programs arose.

Results and Discussions

The system of preschool education in Russia has existed for a long time. And the question of the quality of pre-school education has always been relevant. Until the 1990s, there was the only one “Basic Program of Pre-School Education and Training”. The entire system of preschool development in the USSR was built on the basis of this program, which in fact was a criterion for the quality of preschool education and upbringing.

In 2013, the Federal State Educational Standard for Pre-School Education was adopted, which made it possible to vary the content, methods and techniques of pre-school education. And, of course, the problem of the quality of the educational program was becoming crucial. The variability of programs (i.e. the need for different pre-school education programs that have different goals and offer different ways to achieve them) is an important condition for building a successful pre-school education system in Russia.

International practice shows that assessments of quality of preschool education programs can be focused on various objects and depend on different views on quality. Moreover, the assessment can be focused on the conditions for the implementation of the educational process (educational environment, educational activities, educational conditions, interaction, etc.). This type of quality assessment is defined as “assessment of the educational (developing) environment”, the dynamics of the individual development of pupils (academic performance of children, individual development of the child, different types of children's activity, etc.). This type of quality assessment evaluates the “academic performance of children”. A lot of research and practice in many countries have shown that developing preschool education is closely related to the assessment of the educational environment

One of the most popular, well-known and common methods for assessing the quality of the educational environment is the ECERS scale. It is remarkable that the development of quality preschool education offered by the LMTF initiative and the areas noted in the Federal State Educational Standard for Pre-School Education are similar. All this suggests that the idea of the quality of preschool education in Russia and in international space coincide (see Table 1).

Table 1. Development areas in preschool education: the Federal State Educational Standard for Pre-School Education in Russia and internationally.

Development areas based on the Federal State Educational Standard for Pre-School Education, the Russian Federation	LMTF development areas
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio-communicative development • Speech development • Cognitive development • Artistic and aesthetic development • Physical development 	<p>styles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social and emotional development • Literacy and communication • Cognitive development and learning • Numbers and math operations • Science and technology • Culture and art • Physical well-being
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It is important to understand that the assessment tools are to correspond to the established idea of the quality of preschool education, and this idea is connected with the goal that the national system of preschool education is to achieve.

In the Russian system of preschool education, the academic performance of children cannot be selected as objects of external assessment of the quality of educational activities of an educational institution. In this regards, an acceptable object for assessing the quality of educational activities in the modern normative space of preschool education in Russia is the educational environment.

Since 2016, the kindergarten is an innovative platform of the federal state-maintained institution “Institute for the Study of Childhood, Family and Education at the Russian Academy of Education”. Their goal is the generation and implementation of a system model of education quality management in a pre-school educational institution based on a methodical complex for organizing a pre-school education quality assessment system.

In December 2016 after studying the ECERS scale method with the pre-school staff, we conducted a survey of all groups in the particular pre-school. What did we see? The analysis of the data obtained (Chart 1, 2) showed that the strong regulation of the environment through SanPiN 2.1.3.2630-10 “Sanitary and Epidemiological Requirements for Institutions Engaged in Medical Activity” allows us to show universal and high-level results in terms of environment and safety. However, in terms of interaction, respect for diversity, as well as in terms of a flexible and open learning environment and inclusion, there is a greater potential for development.

1. Chart before the experiment:

In order to raise the level of the subject-spatial environment in groups we divided the group into centers. Later the staff allocated a place for the privacy of children. With the help of parents we collected mini-libraries. The pre-school purchased the “Mate Plus”, box designed various puppets for the pre-school theaters. The staff established cooperation with parents of preschoolers. In 2018, the “Speech-plus” gaming manuals were introduced into work with children for the development of speech. The developing environment is important for children not only in groups, but also in all premises of the pre-school as well as outdoors during the summer period. In the corridors and halls a developing, game space was organized. The Native History Museum was opened and regularly upgraded, the ‘Corner’ of the Traffic Rules was arranged, vertical playbooks were made. The whole environment that surrounds the child has become mobile, multi-functional, and up-to-date. 2 years have passed and the diagram has changed:

2. Chart after the experiment:

2016 year

Subject-spatial environment

Conclusion

Today, educators in preschool institutions bear a great responsibility for the life and upbringing of the younger generation, since everything begins with the educator, his/her attitude towards children and the staff. Education of a preschooler largely depends on education and perception of the world of his/her educator. We all understand that the world will become fast, technological, diverse, so the main goal is a smooth transition of Russian education to a qualitatively new level through the creation of an educational system based on independent quality assessment and creating conditions for self-realization and professional and personal growth of educators.

References

- Heckman J. Policies to foster human capital // *Research in Economics*, 2000 4 Heckman J., Cunha F., Lochner L., Masterov D. Interpreting the evidence on life cycle skill formation // *Handbook of the Economics of Education*, Volume 1. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2006
- Presidential Decree No. 240 of May 29, 2017 “On Declaring a Decade of Childhood in the Russian Federation”. –URL: base.garant.ru/71684480/
- Harms Thelma, Clifford Richard M., Cryer Debbie. ECERS. Scales for a comprehensive assessment of the quality of education in pre-school educational organizations. Moscow: Natsionalnoe obrazovanie, 2016. 116 p.
- Yudina E.G. Quality assessment of preschool education: a comparative analysis of Russian and international practice. Moscow: Federal State Budgetary Establishment of Higher Professional Education “Russian Academy of National Economy and Public Administration under the President of the Russian Federation”, 2015. 54 p.